

The effect of burnout, emotional intelligence and extrovert personality types on teacher performance in senior high school 13 Padang, Indonesia

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Abstract

This study aims to see the effect of (1) burnout on teacher performance Senior High School (SMA)13 Padang. (2) Emotional intelligence on teacher performance at SMA 13 Padang.(3)Extrovert personality type on teacher performance at SMA 13 Padang. (4) Burnout, emotional intelligence and extroverted personality types have a joint effect on teacher performance at SMA 13 Padang. The entire population in this study teachers of SMA 13 Padang as many as 59 people. The technique for taking this sample uses a total sampling technique. The data analysis technique uses multiple linear regression with the classical assumption test, normality test, multicollinearity and heteroscedasticity .The results of this study indicate that (1) Burnout has a significant negative effect on teacher performance at SMA 13 Padang. (2) Emotional intelligence has a positive influence on teacher performance at SMA 13 Padang. (3) Extrovert personality type has a positive influence on teacher performance at SMA 13 Padang. (4) Burnout, Emotional intelligence and Extrovert personality type jointly affect teacher performance at SMA 13 Padang.

Keywords: Burnout; Emotional Intelligence; Extrovert personality type; Padang

1. Introduction

Human resources are a separate challenge for management, because the success of management and others depends on the quality of human resources (Ranihusna, 2010:91). In addition, there are other challenges experienced by agencies, namely the increasing complexity of customer requests to meet their daily needs. Facing competition with other agencies both nationally and internationally, agencies must be able to make changes towards improvement (Nahdluddin & Maftukhah, 2015).

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Good quality human resources can be seen from workers who have a sense of responsibility and are able to make the maximum contribution to the progress of the agency (Yanti et al., 2014: 32). Agencies always want teacher performance to be good, thereby increasing the contribution of teachers, organizations need to implement empowerment programs

One of the biggest challenges facing agencies is ensuring that teacher performance remains stable and even increases (Wahono, 2012). Teacher performance will directly affect organizational performance as an aspect of creating competitive advantage. This makes an understanding of the factors that can affect performance important for

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organizations to carry out, considering that teacher performance is one of the important aspects in achieving the success of an organization (Kappagoda et al., 2014).

Reviewing theoretical and empirical evidence, researchers have identified many factors that can affect performance and divided them into three aspects, namely the teacher's internal, internal environment, and external environment (Wirawan, 2012: 6). Internal factors are factors that originate within the teacher such as burnout (Sukmana & Sudibia, 2015: 2335), emotional intelligence (Nurita, 2012: 2), and Personality Type Tendencies (Afidah & Pratiwi, 2011: 197).

As time goes by, SMA 13 Padang faces strategic issues, namely teacher services that are not yet optimal in teaching, there are still student complaints about existing services, lack of facilities and infrastructure, competition between schools in the vicinity. So it is important for school management to be able to maintain the best performance of their teachers, one of which is by stimulating the performance of their teachers.

Table 1 Performance Data of the Preliminary Study of Teacher Performance at SMA 13 Padang

No	Dimensions	Statement	Agree	Don't agree
1	Working Quantity	The quantity of my work exceeds what the organization expects	8	12
2	Work quality	The results of my work satisfy the leadership	12	8
3	Cooperation	I am able to work well with my co-workers	6	14
4	Responsibility	I take full responsibility for the work I do	9	11
5	initiative	I really like the challenge of a new job	8	12
Total			32	57

Source: Preliminary Survey

Table 1 shows the results of a crew survey on teacher performance at SMA 13 Padang. It can be seen from the table that many teachers expressed disagreement. This condition indicates that there is a problem with the teacher's performance at SMA 13 Padang. Based on the description of the background of the problem, the authors are interested in conducting research with the title "The Influence of Burnout, Emotional Intelligence, and Extrovert Personality Types on Teacher Performance at SMA 13 Padang".

2. Research methods

The population and sample in a study have a central and decisive role (Muri A., 2015). The population is the entire object of study which provides an accurate description of the research. According to Hamid (2015) population is the total number of objects or subjects used as data sources in a study that have the same nature or characteristics. Thus, the population in this study were all teachers at SMA 13 Padang, totaling 59 people.

The technique in taking this sample uses a total sampling technique (overall sample), total sampling is a sampling technique where the number of samples is equal to the population (Sugiyono, 2017). The reason for taking total sampling is because according to (Sugiyono, 2017) the total population is less than 100, the entire population is used as a research sample.

Testing the hypothesis in this study using multiple linear regression analysis. Multiple linear regression analysis aims to determine the causal relationship between the influencing variables and the affected variables. With the multiple regression equation model as follows:

$$Y = a + b_1 X_1 + b_2 X_2 + b_3 X_3 + e \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Where:

- Y = Performance
- a = Intercept constant
- X1 = Burnout
- X2 = Emotional intelligence

X3 = Extrovert personality type
 b1, b2, ... = Regression Coefficient
 e = Error Term

3. Research result

3.1. Classic assumption test

3.1.1. Normality test

This normality test is used by the author to test the normality of the regression model. Testing is done by using the method *kolmogorov-smirnov test* for each variable. The regression model is normally distributed if the Kolmogorov-Smirnov sign value for each variable is greater than $\alpha = 0.05$. The results of the normality test can be seen in table 2.

Table 2 Normality Test Results

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test					
		Y	X1	X2	X3
N		59	59	59	59
Normal Parameters	Means	42.5763	17.5593	42.8136	17.6271
	std. Deviation	2.96068	1.60034	2.32286	1.40072
Most Extreme Differences	absolute	0.116	0.202	0.146	0.198
	Positive	0.095	0.120	0.146	0.141
	Negative	-0.116	-0.202	-0.092	-0.198
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		0.893	1,549	1,121	1,522
asyp. Sig. (2-tailed)		0.403	0.096	0.162	0.219
a. Test distribution is Normal.					

Source: SPSS Output Normality Test Results

From Table 2 above which is a normality test, it can be seen that in the regression model, the confounding or residual variables have a normal distribution. This can be seen from the results of the sig value of the performance variable (Y) which is $0.403 > 0.05$ burnout variable (X1) is $0.096 > 0.05$; emotional intelligence variable (X2) is $0.162 > 0.05$; extrovert personality type variable (X3) is $0.219 > 0.05$. So it can be concluded that the variables of performance, burnout, emotional intelligence, and extroverted personality type and teacher motivation at SMA 13 Padang are normally distributed.

3.2. Multicollinearity Test

Table 3 Multicollinearity Test Results

Coefficients a			
Model		Collinearity Statistics	
		tolerance	VIF
1	Burnout	0.990	1010
	Emotional intelligence	0.986	1014
	Extrovert personality type	0.985	1015
a. Dependent Variable: Y			

Source: SPSS Output Multicollinearity Test Results

Multicollinearity test is useful for testing whether the regression model found a correlation between independent variables. A good regression model should not have a correlation between the independent variables. If the independent variables are correlated, then these variables are not orthogonal. Orthogonal variables are independent variables whose correlation value among independent variables = 0 (Ghozali, 2011). Multicollinearity can be seen from the tolerance and Variance Inflation Factor (VIF). The way to find out whether there are deviations from the multicollinearity test is to look at the Tolerance and VIF values of each independent variable, if the Tolerance value is > 0.10 and the VIF value is < 10, the data is free from multicollinearity symptoms, which can be seen in Table 3.

Based on the multicollinearity test in the table above, it can be seen that there is no relationship between the independent variables because all the values of the VIF independent variables are <10.

3.3. Heteroscedasticity Test

The heteroscedasticity test aims to test whether in a regression model there is an inequality of variance from the residuals from one observation to another. If the variance from the residual of one observation to another observation remains, then it is called homoscedasticity and if it is different it is called heteroscedasticity. To detect the existence of heteroscedasticity in this study using the Scatter Plot test. In this test, if there is no clear pattern, such as the points spreading above and below the number 0 (zero) on the Y axis, then there is no heteroscedasticity. The test results can be seen in Figure 1.

In Figure 1 it can be seen that there is no clear pattern and the points spread above and below the number 0 on the Y axis. This shows that the data in this study did not occur heteroscedasticity.

Figure 1 Heteroscedasticity Test Results

3.4. Research Hypothesis Test

3.4.1. Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

In testing the hypothesis of this study, multiple linear regression tests were used, which aims to determine how much influence the independent variables have on the dependent variable. Multiple regression analysis was performed by comparing t_{count} with t_{table} and sig value with $\alpha = 0.05$. In detail, the results of multiple regression testing can be seen in Table 4.

Table 4 Multiple Regression Equations

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	std. Error	Betas		
1	(Constant)	40.921	10.735		3.812	0.000
	X1	-0.654	0.250	-0.029	-2.616	0.019
	X2	0.539	0.173	0.030	3.115	0.004
	X3	0.454	0.187	0.026	2.428	0.021
a. Dependent Variable: Y						

Source: SPSS Output Multiple Linear Regression Results, 2021

Based on Table 4, the estimation model can be analyzed as follows:

$$Y = 40,921 - 0.654(X1) + 0.539(X2) + 0.454(X3)$$

Based on the equation above it can be explained that:

- From the equation above it can be seen that there is a constant value of 40,921 which means that if burnout, emotional intelligence, and extroverted personality type are zero, then the value of the performance variable is at 40,921. This means that burnout variables, emotional intelligence, and extroverted personality types contribute to improving teacher performance at SMA 13 Padang.
- The value of the burnout regression coefficient is negative 0.654. This means that if work burnout increases by one unit, it will result in an increase in performance of 0.654 unit.
- The value of the regression coefficient of emotional intelligence is positive, namely 0.539. This means that if emotional intelligence increases by one unit, it will result in an increase in teacher performance by 0.539 unit.
- The value of the regression coefficient for the extrovert personality type is positive, namely 0.454. This means that if the extrovert personality type increases by one unit, it will result in an increase in teacher performance by 0.454 unit.

3.5. Regression Coefficient Test (t test)

3.5.1. Hypothesis Testing 1

The first hypothesis put forward, that burnout partially has a negative effect on teacher performance. Based on the results of the analysis of the t test, it is known that the significance level of the burnout variable is $0.019 < 0.05$ of the significance value (0.05). Thus H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. So that the alternative hypothesis proposed in this study is accepted, meaning that there is a significant effect of burnout on teacher performance at SMA 13 Padang.

3.5.2. Hypothesis Testing 2

The second hypothesis put forward, that emotional intelligence partially has a negative effect on teacher performance. Based on the results of the analysis of the t test, it is known that the significance level of the emotional intelligence variable is $0.004 < 0.05$ of the significance value (0.05). Thus H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. So that the alternative hypothesis proposed in this study is accepted, meaning that there is a significant negative effect between emotional intelligence on teacher performance at SMA 13 Padang.

3.5.3. Hypothesis Testing 3

The third hypothesis put forward, that extrovert personality type partially positive effect on performance. Based on the results of the analysis of the t test, it is known that the significance level of the extrovert personality type variable is $0.021 < 0.05$ of the significance value (0.05). Thus H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. So that the alternative hypothesis proposed in this study is accepted, meaning that there is a significant influence between extroverted personality types on teacher performance at SMA 13 Padang.

3.5.4. Hypothesis Testing 4

The fourth hypothesis proposed, that burnout, emotional intelligence, and extrovert personality type and motivation jointly have a positive effect on teacher performance. Based on the results of the analysis of the F test, it is known that the significance level of burnout, emotional intelligence, and extroverted personality type is $0.000 < 0.05$. Thus H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. So that the alternative hypothesis proposed in this study is accepted, meaning that there is a jointly significant effect of burnout, emotional intelligence, and extrovert personality type on teacher performance at SMA 13 Padang. As can be seen in table 5.

Table 5 F test results

ANOVA b						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	71,306	3	14,435	3.047	0.000a
	residual	507,101	55	9,220		
	Total	508,407	58			
a. Predictors: (Constant), X3, X1, X2						
b. Dependent Variable: Y						

Source: SPSS Output F Test Results, 2021

3.6. Coefficient of Determination (R Square)

The coefficient of determination aims to see or measure how far the model's ability to explain the variation of the independent variable, where is the value *R square* used for research with 2 variables and the value of R Square is used for research with more than 3 variables. The coefficient of determination in this study was taken from the R Square value which can be seen in table 6.

Table 6 R Square Test Results

Summary model b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.851	0.724	0.702	3.03645
a. Predictors: (Constant), X3, X1, X2				
b. Dependent Variable: Y				

Source: SPSS R Square Output Test Results, 2021

Based on the results of the analysis R square is 0,724 this means that 72.4% of teacher performance is influenced by the independent variables burnout, emotional intelligence, and extroverted personality type and motivation. While the remaining 28.6% is influenced by other variables outside the model.

4. Discussion

Discussion of research results is intended to explain and interpret research results.

4.1. Influence Burnout of Teacher Performance at SMA 13 Padang.

The results of this study indicate that burnout has a significant positive effect on teacher performance at SMA 13 Padang. This indicates that burnout determines teacher performance at SMA 13 Padang. This means that the better the teacher and agency burnout, the better the teacher's performance.

From the results of this study, it appears that the burnout variable has a coefficient of -0.654 which means burnout has a big influence from other variables. This indicates that burnout can play a role in improving teacher performance. If at SMA 13 Padang you want to improve teacher performance, then you have to reduce teacher burnout in agencies.

This is in line with the opinion according to Sani (2012: 5) burnout is an emotional pressure, constantly or repeatedly caused by interaction and conflict with many people in the long term. And usually this job burnout is experienced by many public service workers, such as teachers, tutors, social services. Limonu (2013: 5) reveals that burnout is a change in attitude and behavior in the form of a reaction to withdraw psychologically from work such as keeping a distance from clients or being cynical, truant, often late and a strong desire to change jobs. In addition, burnout can have an impact on worsening physical, mental and emotional conditions, as well as on teacher work performance, so that it can worsen the image of hospital services, and can further endanger the patient's condition (Lailani, 2012: 69).

The results of this study are in line with researchAsia, (2013) which shows that burnout has a negative and significant effect on teacher performance. Sani (2012) research results also show burnout has a significant negative effect on teacher performance.

4.2. Influence Emotional Intelligence on Teacher Performance at SMA 13 Padang

The results of this study indicate that emotional intelligence has a significant positive influence on teacher performance at SMA 13 Padang. This indicates that the teacher's emotional intelligence determines the teacher's performance at SMA 13 Padang. This means that the better the emotional intelligence of the institution, the teacher's performance will improve.

From the results of this study, it appears that the work emotional intelligence variable has a coefficient 0.539 which means emotional intelligence has a big influence. This indicates that good and good emotional intelligence can play a role in improving teacher performance. If at SMA 13 Padang you want to improve teacher performance, then you have to create emotional intelligence for teachers in existing institutions.

This is in line with the opinion According to Goleman (2002: 411) emotion refers to a feeling and a typical thought, a biological and psychological state and a series of tendencies to act. Emotions are basically urges to act. Usually emotion is a reaction to stimuli from outside and within the individual. Furthermore, Goleman (2006: 512) reveals that emotional intelligence is a person's ability to manage his emotional life with intelligence, maintain emotional harmony and express it through self-awareness skills, self-control, self-motivation, empathy, and social skills.

The results of this study are in line with Duwit's research (2015) which shows that emotional intelligence affects teacher performance. Nurita (2012) research results also show that emotional intelligence has a significant effect on teacher performance.

4.3. Influence Extrovert Personality Types on Teacher Performance at SMA 13 Padang

The results of this study indicate that the extroverted personality type has a significant effect on teacher performance at SMA 13 Padang. This indicates that the extroverted personality type determines the teacher's performance at SMA 13 Padang. This means that the better and better the extroverted personality type of the teacher to the agency will improve the teacher's performance.

From the results of this study, it appears that the extrovert personality type variable has a coefficient 0.454 which means that the extrovert personality type has a big influence. This indicates that the extrovert personality type can play a role in improving teacher performance. If at SMA 13 Padang you want to improve teacher performance, then you have to increase the extroverted personality type of work for teachers in agencies.

This is in accordance with the opinion (Alwisol, 2009: 7). Alwisol explained that types can be interpreted similar to traits, but in a more limited group of stimuli. Meanwhile, personality is a descriptive description of behavior without giving value. Based on these two terms it can be concluded that personality type is a special trait that describes a person's behavior. Furthermore Eysenck in Alwisol (2009: 255) says that personality type is a characteristic of an individual who can describe his behavior, thoughts and emotions and can be observed which characterizes a person in dealing with the world.

The results of this study are in line with the research of Kour & Sharma, (2013) which shows that there is a significant positive effect between extroverted personality types on teacher performance.

4.4. Effects of Burnout, Emotional Intelligence, and Extroverted Personality Types on Teacher Performance at SMA 13 Padang

The results of this study indicate that burnout, emotional intelligence, and extroverted personality types and motivation together have a significant influence on teacher performance at SMA 13 Padang. This indicates that burnout, emotional intelligence, and extroverted personality types determine teacher performance at SMA 13 Padang. This means that good burnout, emotional intelligence, and extroverted personality types will improve teacher performance.

This is in line with the research of Kour & Sharma, (2013), Duwit (2015) which shows that the results show support for a positive and significant influence between burnout, emotional intelligence, and extroverted personality types on teacher performance.

5. Conclusion

Based on the results of the testing and discussion of the hypotheses described in the previous chapter, several conclusions can be drawn as follows:

- Burnout has a negative influence on teacher performance at SMA 13 Padang. This means that the teacher's performance will increase if the burnout in the institution decreases and the teacher has a low value so that he is able to provide encouragement to the teacher in improving his performance. conversely, the lower the teacher burnout level at MAN 13 Padang, the teacher's performance will increase.
- Emotional intelligence has a positive influence on teacher performance at SMA 13 Padang. This means that the teacher's performance will increase if good emotional intelligence is able to provide enthusiasm for the teacher in carrying out the work. The better the emotional intelligence of a teacher in an institution, the better his performance in carrying out his work in that institution.
- The extrovert personality type has a positive influence on teacher performance at SMA 13 Padang. This means that the teacher's performance will increase if the extrovert personality type is a good agency for the teacher, so that the teacher becomes enthusiastic and can do the job well. And a good extrovert personality type will encourage high performance.
- Burnout, emotional intelligence, and extrovert personality type and motivation together have a positive effect on teacher performance at SMA 13 Padang. With the Anova F Test score of $0.000 < 0.05$, thus the teacher's performance is influenced by the independent variables burnout, emotional intelligence, and extroverted personality type, and motivation.

Suggestion

Based on the results of the discussion analysis and some conclusions in this study, suggestions that can be given through the results of this study in order to get better results, namely:

For future researchers, it is hoped that they can examine other variables outside of this variable in order to obtain more varied results that can describe what things can affect performance and it is advisable to expand the scope of research on the effects of burnout, emotional intelligence, and extroverted personality types and motivation on teacher performance used in this study.

For agency management, it is expected to create good emotional intelligence between teachers, leaders in agencies. Because to achieve productivity and achieve better agency goals requires burnout, good emotional intelligence, motivation, a high and good extrovert personality type also in teachers and institutions as well as teacher loyalty. When burnout, emotional intelligence, and extroverted personality types, and motivation are given in a balanced way, the teacher's performance also increases.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Statement of informed consent

All individuals in this research survey agreed with this study

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